

The Symbolic Significance of the Christmas Tree Drawing

Madeline Foong Yee Wong, BA

Consultant & Credentialed Dialogic-Diagnostic Arts Therapist

Training Facilitator, Almond Tree Training & NeuroLAT, Singapore

Guo-Hui Xie, Ed.D, BCET, BCSE

Academic Chair, Merlion Academy, Singapore

Principal Therapist, Paediatric Therapy Centre, Singapore

APA Citation: Wong, M. F. Y., & Xie, G. H. (2022). The symbolic significance of the Christmas tree drawing. *Early Years Research*, 2(2), 17-22.

Abstract

Christmas Day falls on the 25th day in the month of December each year and is associated with a religious celebration of the birth of Jesus by the Christians – both the Roman Catholics and the Protestants as well as other Christians from different denominations – worldwide. In fact, there are several hypotheses regarding the exact date of Jesus' birth. However, in the early 4th Century AD, the Western churches fixed the date as 25 December, while the Eastern churches put it on 7 January of the following year. Christmas has also become a cultural and commercial event associated with iconic figures such as Santa Claus, reindeer, snowy winter, snowman, and, of course, not forgetting the Christmas tree. Today, what is known about the special occasion has almost been lost or drowned in commercialism. In this short paper, the authors explored the historical and religious symbolism of the Christmastide through the projective drawing of a Christmas tree (suitable for both children and adults), and what this fun activity can offer to help drawers of all ages to understand the true meaning behind the celebration of Christmas.

Key Words: Christmas Day, Christmastide, Christmas tree, Draw-a-Tree, Jesus Christ

Introduction

As each year comes to a gradual close, Christmas comes into the picture. According to Lizorkin-Eyzenberg (2022), “[N]owhere in the Holy Scriptures are we told about a celebration commemorating the birth of Christ Jesus” (para. 1). In fact, “[T]he first church figure to discuss the date of Jesus’ birth was Clement (c.200), an Egyptian preacher from Alexandria” (Lizorkin-Eyzenberg, 2022, para. 3). By the middle of the 4th Century AD, the Western churches were already celebrating the birth of Christ on 25 December (Roll, 1995), while the Eastern churches did so on 7 January in the following year. It is important to note that “it was not until the 4th to 6th centuries of the Common Era that Christians began to ‘Christianize’ the local pagan celebrations of the peoples they sought to evangelize” (Lizorkin-Eyzenberg, 2022, para. 7).

Christmas Day, which is primarily observed by several branches of Eastern Christianity on 25 December¹ each year based on the Julian calendar, is an annual festival commemorating the birth of Jesus Christ among billions of people

throughout the world. It is a feast central to the Christian liturgical year, preceded by the season of Advent (also known as the Nativity Fast), and the special occasion initiates the season of Christmastide. Historically, Christmastide in the West lasts 12 days and culminates on Twelfth Night² (see Forbes, 2008, for detail) – remember the popular song *The Twelve Days of Christmas* written by the English composer Frederic Austin (b.1872-d.1952), whose version of the song and the melody only became popular in 1909. Unlike the majority of the churches, the Armenian churches observed the nativity on January 6 even before the Gregorian calendar originated. There are also some Armenian churches using the Julian calendar to celebrate Christmas Day on January 19 on the Gregorian calendar, with January 18 being Christmas Eve.

¹ Christmas Day based on the Gregorian calendar is celebrated on January 7 each year. Most Armenian Christians use the Gregorian calendar, still celebrating Christmas Day on January 6.

² According to Forbes (2008), “In 567AD, the Council of Tours proclaimed that the entire period between Christmas and Epiphany should be considered part of the celebration, creating what became known as the 12 days of Christmas, or what the English called Christmastide. On the last of the 12 days, called Twelfth Night, various cultures developed a wide range of additional special festivities. The variation extends even to the issue of how to count the days. If Christmas Day is the first of the 12 days, then Twelfth Night would be on January 5, the eve of Epiphany” (p. 27).

Today, Christmas has been declared a public holiday in many countries except for Muslim countries and a few other countries (e.g., China and North Korea). It is now celebrated religiously by a majority of Christians (Ehorn, Hewlett, & Hewlett, 1995) as well as culturally by many non-Christians (Hytrek, 2009), and has become a special occasion of gift giving and sharing of the festive joy, goodwill and glad tidings among all people, young and old.

In this paper, the authors have chosen to focus on the symbolism of the Christmas tree, its significance and what its archetypal meaning.

The Cross, the Tree

Among the Christian symbols, the Cross is most widely used and known throughout the world. It has become the universal symbol of Christianity representing God's redemption for sinful mankind through Christ Jesus who was crucified on the Cross or hung on the Tree. In other words, the Cross and the Tree mean the same thing here. According to Brasseaux (2015), when the Holy Bible mentions that Jesus was hung on a *tree*, he explained that the word *tree* is being used in the general sense to refer to 'a structure made of wood' (para. 12) – more of an archaic word which carries the poetic/literary definition of *tree*. 'It was *not* a tree in the sense of Jesus being nailed to something growing in the ground with branches and leaves' (Brasseaux, 2015, para. 12). It was referring denotatively to some type of wooden structure, a tree that had already been cut down, stripped of leaves and branches, and trimmed into beams that could be carried by men (for more detail, see Matthew 27:32; Mark 15:21; Luke 23:26; John 19:17 in the New Testament of the Holy Bible).

The Cross itself has multiple meanings and hence, it can mean different things to different people. 'Some have it displayed on their mantel, others wear it around their neck' (Coleman, 2022, para. 2). According to Coleman (2022), the Cross means (i) love and (ii) a portrayal of willful humility; it is also (iii) personal, (iv) prophetic, and (v) final when Christ uttered His last words, while still being hung on the cruel tree, "It is finished" found in the gospel according to Saint John (Chapter 19, Verse 30). The Greek word translated "it is finished" is *tetelestai* - an accounting term that means 'paid in full' (Jenkins, 2020, para. 1). It also means that Christ has provided the only solution to the sin of mankind: the only way to God is through Himself (see John 14:6; Acts 4:12). It is only through the death of Christ that Christians can put to death their sin and put on Christ (Colossians 3:5-14).

The Cross is the agent of redemption. This is the doctrine of *redemptionism* whose advent began with Rev Michael Williams, a traditional Evangelical Christian, in the early 1990s. It is '[T]he doctrine that all of humanity was redeemed (i.e., saved, sanctified) through the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ and asserting that the redemption of all was completed and concluded in His resurrection. There was no further need for scriptural fulfillment thereafter' (Mike Williams Gospel, 2016, para. 2).

The Tree as a Symbol of being redeemed from every Curse

Christ has redeemed us from the curse of the law, having become a curse for us (for it is written, "Cursed is everyone who hangs on a tree"), that the blessing of Abraham might come upon the Gentiles in Christ Jesus, that we might receive the promise of the Spirit through faith. (Galatians 3:13-14; New King James Version³)

In the above passage from the Bible, in Galatians 3:13-14, the curse of Jesus Christ for all believers is clear. This is how all the blessings that God wants to give fallen mankind can be realized. Jesus died for sinners, in their place. The death he suffered was not his because the sin was not his, the sin was not his, and the punishment he endured was not his.

The method by which Jesus died on the tree also makes sense for several reasons. Crucifixion, hanging the convicts on a wooden cross, was reserved for the vilest criminals. Criminals are often left to die by slow suffocation (when their lungs collapse after bearing the full weight of their body) in a very public space. This means that the location of the cross with the criminals being crucified will likely be along busy streets. This should serve as a warning to everyone that the consequences of this intrusion are huge. Roman citizens were rarely executed this way. When Jesus was executed by crucifixion, he became the most shameful sinner before a holy God, who placed upon him the sin of all those for whom he died. Since being hanged from a tree meant that Jesus would be in sight of everyone in a crowd on a busy street, it means that this very public form of execution was witnessed by a lot of people during this period.

Being crucified on a tree means that Jesus carries within him the covenant curse that Adam's rebellion has inflicted on all mankind. Ignoring God's clear command to not do so, Adam ate from the tree of the knowledge of good and evil, and the

³ Testament, N., & Psalms, P. (1987). The New King James Version. Tennessee: National Publishing Company.

curse of eternal death fell upon him and all who came after him.

Deuteronomy 21:22-23 states that if a man has committed a sin deserving of death, and he is put to death and hung on a tree, he who is hanged is accursed of God. Jesus, who is also known as the last Adam, was hung from a tree to redeem mankind from all the curses caused by Adam's rebellion. Even the curse mentioned in Galatians 3:13 (which was quoted from Deuteronomy 21:22-23) must be fully included in the act of redemption.

Thus, the innocent and blessed Son of God was hung from a tree as if He were a vile criminal, and He suffered the wrath of God on our behalf, bringing all the curses upon Himself, so we can experience all the blessings of the new covenant.

Christian Symbols related to Christmas Celebration

There are also many other Christian symbols besides the prominent symbol of the Cross. These symbols include angel, blood, bread, door, dove, heart, light, love, and water. Among the symbols, it is during the Christmas festive season that one can find most Christian symbols displayed widely everywhere, such as the Star of Bethlehem, the Magi (i.e., the three Kings of the East who came to worship Christ when He was born), an angel blowing a trumpet hearkening to the birth of Christ, and many more.

In this short paper, the authors' focus is targeted on the Christian symbols relevant to the Christmas celebration. However, to begin, we need to know and understand what Christmas is and how it came about.

The celebration of Christmas, which was originally known as Christ's Mass, started in Rome about AD 336. However, for the first 300 years of Christianity, it was not a celebration of Christ's birth. According to Graves (2020), found 'in an old list of Roman bishops, compiled in AD 354, the following words appeared for AD 336: "25 Dec.: natus Christus in Betleem Judeae" (para. 1). It means 'December 25th, Christ born in Bethlehem, Judea.' This is the day, December 25, 336, that has been recorded as the first celebration of Christmas. However, it did not become a major Christian festival until the 9th century. The early Christian community distinguished between the identification of the date of Jesus' birth and the liturgical celebration of that event. The actual observance of the day of Jesus' birth was long in coming.

Among the Christian symbols that we often see during the Christmas season is the prominent Christmas tree. Nobody is certain exactly when the

Christmas tree came into the picture. In Christianity, it is a symbol of the birth and resurrection of Jesus Christ. The branches of a Christmas tree and the shrubs are often viewed as an emblem of immortality. They symbolize the crown of thorns to be worn by Christ when He was falsely accused and sentenced to death by being crucified on the Cross (or figuratively speaking, hung on the Tree of Death).

According to Graves (2020), there was an interesting myth that originated in Germany - quite popular in the 15th century - tells a story of an 8th century English missionary, Saint Boniface, Apostle to Germany, who thwarted a pagan human sacrifice under an oak tree by cutting down that tree. In its place, a fir tree grew with its branches representing a symbol of the everlasting Christ and His eternal truth. By the end of the 16th century, Christmas trees were common in Germany. Some say it was the reformist, Saint Martin Luther, who cut the first Christmas tree, took it home and decked it with candles to represent the stars. When the German court came to England, the Christmas tree came with them.

Symbolic Meaning of Christmas Tree

The Christmas tree symbolizes the birth of Jesus Christ. It is also a representation of the Tree of Life in the Garden of Eden and it is also a reminder that we are all children of God who should love one another. There are also many other symbolic meanings for the Christmas tree. A cut or chopped-down Christmas tree symbolizes our fallen world, sinful human nature. An uncut and undecorated Christmas tree symbolizes the plain message of salvation for mankind through Christ Jesus - the pinnacle of God's redemption for us.

Christmas Tree Drawing (CTD)

Like the Tree Drawing Test (TDT; Koch, 1949), also known as Koch's Baum Test, drawing a Christmas tree (or Christmas Tree Drawing) has become itself a form of projective drawing activity, but *not* a projective drawing test *per se*, that can tell us something about what a drawer, be s/he a child, adolescent or adult, is aware of Christmas and the symbolic meaning that underlies the special occasion of celebration. The instruction is simple: "Draw a Christmas tree."

The purpose of the Christmas Tree Drawing (CTD) is very much related to the Christian faith. Most Christians attach the Christmas symbols to their faith. Hence, the CTD tells us about a drawer's degree of his/her spiritual attachment to what s/he believes. The catholic purpose of red and green colors resonates with the blood shed by Jesus and the everlasting life one gets when one surrenders one's life to Christ Jesus, respectively.

Colors of Christmas in CTD

The colors of Christmas used in CTD refer to those colors that traditionally symbolize Christmas. The two key colors are a medium red and green, which originated with the leaves and berries of holly. According to Spacey (2020), “[T]he evergreen varieties of holly plants constitute the traditional symbol of Christianity and have been used since the Medieval Age to make Christmas wreaths” (para. 1). Spacey (2020) has identified 14 colors associated with Christmas such as blue, gold, grey, pink, purple, red, silver, white and shades of green, and these signature colors help with marketing and branding products related to Christmas (Andersen, 2022).

According to Andersen (2022), the five significant Christmas colors are listed alphabetically as follows with their respective symbolic meanings provided (para. 10-14):

1. **Gold:** This bright shiny color represents the sun as well as the Son (meaning the Son of God, i.e., Jesus Christ). It is used at Christmastime to symbolize light has broken into the darkness. It is also taken to represent one of the gifts that the Magi (or commonly known as the Wise Men from the East) brought before the infant Jesus to adore and worship Him with reverence. The metallic color gold conveys wealth, prosperity and glamour.
2. **Green:** This is one key Christmas color because evergreen plants (e.g., holly and mistletoe) are used at Christmastime. It symbolizes Christ’s life and eternal nature. During the olden pagan era, these evergreen plants served as a reminder that nature keeps growing even during the cold times. The color green often symbolizes money, good luck and health.
3. **Purple:** This rich shade or purple or violet symbolizes holiness. It is also the main color of Advent, the period before Christmas, when Christians throughout the world fast and repent in anticipation of Christ’s birth. The color purple symbolizes royalty, luxury and a sense of magic or whimsy.
4. **Red:** This deep hue symbolizes the blood of Jesus Christ. It was He that Christmas celebrates but Jesus was never born on the Christmas Day. Moreover, in secular sense, the color red also associates with Santa Claus and his distinctive red outfit. Generally, red represents love, courage and romance.
5. **White:** This color is associated with the blanket of fresh white snow that is often seen the Christmas picturesque, especially in the northern hemisphere. The color white hearkens

back to the times of pagan winter solstice festivals. It represents purity and the triumph of good over evil; these are the two main themes at Christmastime.

The colors green and red listed in the Christmas colors should not be confused and misinterpreted as colors of personality (Hammer, 1968; Jolles, 1957; Precker, 1950; also see Rabin, 1968, for detail). Red, may be related to violence or excessive emotion, but it is also associated with cheerfulness, especially when young children use the color in their drawings. The emphasis of red in this aspect suggests “happier, well-adjusted, and more emotional in their personal reactions” (Klepsch & Logie, 1982, p. 35). Green, like blue, is similar in its symbolic meaning, represents “controlled behavior” (Klepsch & Logie, 1982, p. 35).

CTD Symbolic Interpretation

A drawer may add many colorful decorations to his/her Christmas Tree Drawing. Each of these decorations has its own symbolic meaning. Here the authors have provided a list of 12 key Christmas objects that are often used in decorating the Christmas tree and provided their respective symbolic meanings.

1. **Candles:** When added to the CTD, they represent the 'Star of Bethlehem'. Different colored candles mean different things, e.g., white means purity, and pink means joy. Instead of drawing Candles, Christmas Lights are more widely seen in drawing especially when a drawer adds ornamental balls of different colors. These lights represent the new light or hope that Christ is. It also means spending meaningful time together as a family with a refreshed hope for a better future. Like candles, different colored lights mean different things: e.g., white means purity and pink means joy. The lights and candles represent the Star that guided the three Wise Men (the Magi). It can also mean making one’s candle shine and light one’s path in one’s life: positive Christian living. The lit candle also represents Jesus, the light of the world, and candlelight Christmas Eve church services are popular Christmas celebrations in many countries
2. **Candy Cane:** The Christian legend of the candy cane claimed that the shape of the candy is actually a “J” for Jesus and that the red and white stripes represent the blood Jesus spilled and His purity, respectively.
3. **Christmas Angel:** Traditionally, a Christmas angel is the tree topper, placed at the apex of a Christmas tree, to represent the role of angels at the birth of Jesus, e.g., informing the Virgin Mary that she would be the mother of Jesus, visiting Joseph in a dream to tell him that his

role as Jesus's father on Earth, and, most importantly, appearing in the sky over Bethlehem to announce and celebrate Jesus's birth.

4. **Christmas Garland (also Evergreen Tree):** This refers to the evergreen boughs which are a part of winter celebrations for countless centuries, and the Winter Solstice has long had an evergreen holiday garland among its many traditions. The evergreen originally provided inspirational persistence to help people get through the cold, dark days of winter. When Christianity came along, the Christmas celebration simply adapted this custom. However, as the years have passed, most Christmas garland has morphed into something completely different today.
5. **Christmas Presents:** The tradition of Christmas presents takes its roots in the celebration of the Epiphany. It symbolizes the remembrance of the gifts the Magi gave to Jesus when He was born. By extrapolation, it means to show our love and appreciation for others. That is why Christmas is the time when everyone exchange presents with each other.
6. **Christmas Star (also known as the 'Star of Bethlehem'):** According to the Biblical story, the Christmas Star shining sparkly and bright, guided the three wise men from the East (also known as the Magi), to the baby Jesus. The Christmas Star symbolizes Christ's birth on that first Christmas night. The wise men followed the new Star to the babe born in Bethlehem. In a projective tree, if the Star is added, it symbolizes the drawer's desire for the Light in his/her life and to be wise just like the Magi. The Star also stands for hope for humanity.
7. **Christmas Wreath:** Included in the CTD, the wreath represents eternal life (Painter, 2022). Traditional wreaths are in the form of a circle. This circle represents the eternal presence of God, with no beginning and no end, the hope of eternal life through Christ, the Savior, and the unending love of God. Many Christians also see the colors as being inspired by the life of Jesus, with evergreen leaves representing the everlasting life of Christ and the red berries decorations representing the bloodshed during His crucifixion.
8. **Dove:** In CTD, the inclusion of a dove symbolizes peace on Earth that comes through Jesus Christ.
9. **Poinsettia:** It was first introduced to the United States by Joel Poinsett (b.1779-d.1851), an American linguist, scientist, horticulturist, and also a missionary to Mexico. The plant was named after him sometime in the 19th century in honor of his missionary work. As far as the symbolism of poinsettia goes, there

is a lot. To the ancient Aztecs, they called the plant Cuitlaxochitl (or 'star flower'), whose color red symbolizes purity. The poinsettia is also a symbol of motherhood. An ancient remedy in Mexico prescribed a decoction of the red floral leaves of poinsettia to nursing mothers to increase their milk production. Moreover, poinsettia also symbolizes joy, love, hope, and holiness, too.

10. **Snowflake:** Snowflakes have many positive meanings and they symbolize joy, delicacy, clarity, and transformation. They also constitute a sign of the joy and magic of winter. However, its most important symbolic meaning is that of uniqueness because every snowflake is different.
11. **Stocking:** A longing for something that the drawer desires so much.

Conclusion

The Christmas Tree Drawing (CTD) should not in any way be taken as a formal or informal projective drawing test, but as an activity of fun to help drawers to understand the symbolic meaning behind the celebration of Christmas. The authors of this paper want to emphasize their stance to caution readers never to use this projective drawing tool as some kind of an assessment or measurement of one's spiritual growth or maturity or the level of Christian faith. However, it can be used as an ice-breaking activity during Christmas gatherings or parties among Christians and non-Christians to learn about true event behind the historical and religious symbolism of Christmas celebration.

May the spark and joy of Christmas fill the heart of everyone during this season of celebration!

References

- Andersen, C. H. (2022, October 18). What are the Christmas colors, and what do they mean? Retrieved from: <https://www.rd.com/article/christmas-colors-green-red/>.
- Brasseaux, S. (2015, April 26). Why does the Bible say Jesus was hanged on a 'tree'? Retrieved from: <https://forwhatsaiththescrptures.org/2015/04/26/jesus-hanged-on-a-tree/>.
- Coleman, S. (2022, March 28). What is the meaning of the cross? Retrieved from: <https://www.crosswalk.com/special-coverage/lent/what-is-the-meaning-of-the-cross.html>.
- Ehorn, L. E., Hewlett, S. J., & Hewlett, D. M. (1995). *December holiday customs*. Dayton, OH: Lorenz Educational Press.
- Forbes, B. D. (2008). *Christmas: A candid history*. University of California Press.

- Graves, D. (2020, October 23). The first recorded celebration of Christmas. Retrieved from: <https://www.christianity.com/church/church-history/timeline/301-600/the-1st-recorded-celebration-of-christmas-11629658.html>.
- Hammer, E. F. (1968). Projective drawings. In A. I. Rabin (Ed.), *Projective techniques in personality assessment* (pp. 366-393). New York, NY: Springer.
- Hytrek, N. (2009, November 14). Non-Christians focus on secular side of Christmas. *Sioux City Journal*. Retrieved from: https://siouxcityjournal.com/lifestyles/leisure/non-christians-focus-on-secular-side-of-christmas/article_9914761e-ce50-11de-98cf-001cc4c03286.html.
- Jenkins, D. (2020, January 17). What is the meaning and significance of 'It is finished'? Jesus' words in John 19:30. Retrieved from <https://www.christianity.com/wiki/bible/meaning-and-significance-of-john-1930-it-is-finished.html>.
- Jolles, I. A. (1957). Some advances in interpretation of the chromatic phase of the H-T-P. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 13, 81-83.
- Klepsch, M., & Logie, L. (1982). Children draw and tell: An introduction to projective uses of children's human figure drawings. New York, NY: Brunner/Mazel.
- Lizorkin-Eyzenberg, E. (2022, August 18). Is Christmas a pagan holiday? [In private email correspondence].
- Painter, S. (2022) Christmas Wreath Meaning: Traditions & Symbolism. Retrieved from: https://christmas.lovetoknow.com/Christmas_Wreath_Meaning
- Precker, J. A. (1950). Painting and drawing in personality assessment. *Journal of Projective Techniques*, 14, 262-286.
- Rabin, A. I. (Ed.) (1968). *Projective techniques in personality assessment: A modern introduction*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Roll, Susan K. (1995). *Toward the origins of Christmas*. Leuven, Belgium: Peeters Publishers.
- Spacey, J. (2020, May 17). 14 types of Christmas colors. Retrieved from: <https://simplicable.com/en/christmas-colors#:~:text=Christmas%20colors%20are%20colors%20that%20traditionally%20symbolize%20Christmas,.,since%20the%20middle%20ages%20to%20make%20Christmas%20wreaths>.
- Testament, N., & Psalms, P. (1987). The New King James Version. *Tennessee: National Publishing Company*.
- Williams Ministries (2016). Redemptionism. Retrieved from: <https://www.gospelrevolution.com/redemptionism/>.